

Drought resistance

Rasi, a drought-tolerant variety

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During 1979 dry season (Mar-Jul) AICRIP coordinated two trials with 17 entries, each grown in randomized block design with 3 replications at RAU, Pusa campus (25.59°N, 85.40°E, and 51.81 m above sea level). Recommended cultural

techniques were used to raise a good crop. Unfortunately the trial could not be irrigated for 15 days (starting middle of May) during the vegetative growth stage, 33 days after transplanting. Leaf firing was visible after a week of water stress. Total precipitation until harvest was 800 mm, including 637 mm in July. Only Rasi (IET1444) did not have leaf firing drought symptoms. Leaf firing intensity varied from 15 to 50% of the leaf blade for other varieties. Rasi yields under

Rasi yield performance under drought stress, Samastipur, India, 1979.

Variety	Days to 50% flowering	Grain yield (t/ha)
Rasi (IET1444)	99	3.7
Ratna	108	1.5
Pusa 2-21	108	1.9
Saket-4 (CR44-35)	102	3.1
CD (5%)	—	0.65
CV %	—	23.20

drought conditions were promising (see table). □

Temperature tolerance

HPU741, a promising early, cold-tolerant rice variety

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HPU741, a cold-tolerant rice variety selected for earliness and uniform maturity, and designated as IR3941-45-Plp2B from the cross CR126-42-5/IR2061-213, is suitable for cultivation in low, mid, and high hills of Himachal Pradesh up to 1,550 m altitudes.

In transplanted experiments conducted throughout Himachal Pradesh from 1977 to 1982, HPU741 yield averaged 3.7 t/ha – 19.4% more than IR579, 5.7% more than China 988, and 8.8% more than Himdhan (Table 1).

In rainfed upland experiments from 1980 to 1982, it averaged 2.8 t/ha, 27.3% more than China 988 and 16.7% more than Himdhan (Table 1). Table 2 shows that tests in rainfed uplands experienced severe to moderate drought stress from flowering to maturity.

Yield stability parameters for 20 rices tested in the elite varieties trials in

Table 1. Grain yield of HPU741 in Himachal Pradesh, India.^a

Year	Grain yield (t/ha)			
	HPU741	China 988 (check)	Himdhan (check)	IR579 (check)
<i>Transplanted experiments</i>				
1977	3.9 (5)	3.5 (5)	3.6 (5)	—
1978	3.7 (7)	3.6 (7)	4.0 (7)	3.5 (7)
1979	3.8 (6)	3.3 (6)	3.3 (6)	2.5 (6)
1980	3.7 (16)	3.0 (11)	3.0 (16)	3.0 (8)
1981	3.8 (14)	3.9 (9)	3.7 (14)	3.5 (7)
1982	3.4 (9)	3.8 (5)	3.3 (9)	2.6 (5)
Mean	3.1 (57)	3.5 (43)	3.4 (57)	3.1 (33)
Increase over respective checks (%)	—	5.7	8.8	19.4
<i>Rainfed upland experiments</i>				
1980	2.3 (3)	2.1 (3)	2.4 (3)	—
1981	3.4 (4)	2.8 (4)	3.8 (4)	—
1982	2.6 (8)	1.9 (8)	1.7 (8)	—
Mean	2.8 (15)	2.2 (15)	2.4 (15)	—
Increase over respective checks (%)	—	27.3	16.7	—

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the number of locations for which yields were averaged.

Table 2. Rainfall pattern during flowering to maturity period of direct-seeded rice in rainfed uplands, Palampur, H. P. India, 1980-82.^a

1980	Rainfall (mm)	1981	Rainfall (mm)	1982	Rainfall (mm)
1-12 Sep	124.1 (10)	1-2 Sep	45.7 (1)	1-6 Sep	— (6)
13-23 Sep	— (11)	3-14 Sep	— (12)	7-14 Sep	33.4 (4)
24-25 Sep	21.0 (2)	15-21 Sep	125.3 (4)	15-21 Sep	— (7)
26 Sep to 7 Oct	— (12)	20-23 Sep	— (4)	22 Sep	7.6 (1)
8 Oct	8.2 (1)	24-29 Sep	39.6 (4)	23 Sep to 7 Oct	— (15)
9-15 Oct	— (7)	30 Sep to 15 Oct	— (16)	8-9 Oct	10.2 (2)
				10-15 Oct	— (6)

^aFigures in parentheses indicate the number of rainy/dry days.